

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

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INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

Rayimova Sug'diyona Dilmurodovna,
Student, UzSWLU
sugdiyonarayimova07@gmail.com

Barotova Madina Boymurod qizi,
Student, UzSWLU
madinabarotova425@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor:
Durdona Khamidova,
Teacher, UzSWLU
Dhamidova10@gmail.com

Abstract. This article discusses the issues of innovative technologies in education, namely digital divide, effectiveness and learning outcomes, engagement or destruction. Furthermore, technology should not replace traditional teaching methods as the important use of technology in a smart way that helps intercultural competence and provide students with necessary skills to succeed in divers and technology-driven society. The goal of the research is clarify information the advantages and disadvantages of using modern devices in education and classical methods.

Keywords: innovative technology, technological tools, traditional methods, digital, critical thinking.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы инновационных технологий в образовании, а именно цифровое неравенство эффективность и результаты обучение. Важное использование технологий разумным способом который помогает межкультурной компетентности и дает студентам необходимые навыки для достижения успеха в дайверском и технологически ориентированном обществе. Цель исследования уточнить информататках использования современных устройств в обучении и классических методов.

We are now living in a cutting age world. At the same time, the influence of modern technologies is the big part of the education. Compared to past, there is access of using computers, internet connections, electronic tools in a classroom as the result of this students can complete any tasks easily way by using modern gadgets. Besides that, there are several advantages, one of which is unexpected circumstances in our life. For example, COVID-19. During the pandemic, teachers taught their students through online. It's beneficial for students studying and safety. However, despite the many advantages of modern technologies, there are many issues and problems;

Digital divide: Not every student has equal access to dependable internet connections or technology. Due to the unequal playing field this produces, certain pupils gain more than others. Imagine having pupils in your class who can engage in

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interactive simulations while others find it difficult to use even the most basic internet sites.

Attention spans and distraction: Technology might be interesting but it can also be a big source of distraction. Game, social media updates and other internet content can divert students. In a classroom full of technology, teaching pupils appropriate online conduct and cultivating digital citizenship are essential to maintaining concentration. Nowadays, many people struggle with this problem because it also impacts on people's memory. Moreover, many researchers and scientists also learn this. For example, according to Bidarra and Russian (2017), technology and pedagogy are the two pillars for constructing an effective blended learning environment. Their research suggests that simply incorporating technology isn't enough. For a blended learning environment to truly succeed, it needs to be thoughtfully designed by combining powerful educational practices (pedagogy) with the advantages of technology. Moreover, as a result of this, people are starting to become impatient. This situation also affects their daily life.

Teacher-Student relationship: Due to modern technology communication barrier between student and teacher might misunderstand via asynchronous communication, such as emails and online group chats. A straightforward query may be put a wrong interpretation on the absence of gesture and in-person communication. Furthermore, students may find it more difficult to ask assistance from teachers to feel comfortable expressing themselves as the result.

While traditional lesson methods tend to be less useful, innovative pedagogical technologies can not replace it. This means that modern technologies may increase unproductiveness of education through the introduction of innovative, interactive case technologies in teaching. Conventional education frequently places a strong emphasis on fundamental abilities including written and spoken communication, problem-solving, critical thinking. These abilities, independent of technology breakthroughs are essential for success in any field. Assignments such as essays, debates and in-class discussions help students to think critically, express themselves clearly, build excellent communication skills. Take peeragogy and paragogy for example, this peer-learning pedagogy emphasizes the collaborative creation and sharing of knowledge among peers in an interactive, ongoing process (Mulholland, 2019). It fosters a co-creative learning environment in which students actively participate in knowledge-building process (Jamaludin et al 2020).

The development of modern forms of innovative new technologies of education is crucial for addressing the evolving needs of learners in the 21st century. These

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technologies offer new ways to engage students, personalize learning experience. Although technology is a useful tool, it should not precede over the the value of developing critical thinking skills and human contact we can build an educational future where innovative empowers educators, encourages intercultural competency and gives kids the tools they need to succeed in a diverse and fast changing world by tackling these issues and utilizing technology wisely.

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